

Metal bound azo anion radicals[†]

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Using azopyridine ligands (L) the first anion radical complexes of ruthenium(II) have been synthesized using hydridic starting materials which supply both the metal and the reducing equivalent. Species incorporating Ru^{II}(L⁻), Ru^{II}(L⁻)₂ and Ru^{II}(L)(L⁻) fragments have been isolated, the coligands being PPh₃, Cl⁻, CO and H⁻. Weak acids including water readily convert the radicals to nonradical species. The X-ray structure, spectra, EHMO frontier orbitals, magnetism and electrochemistry of the species have been scrutinized and correlated.

Among catenated nitrogen compounds, N-N bond orders of 1 and 2 occur as in hydrazines and azo compounds, respectively. The intermediate bond order 1.5 corresponds to the anion radical state formed by addition of an electron to the azo-π* orbital as in eq. (1). Reductive generation of azo anion radicals in solution has been known for long¹⁻⁴ but their isolation in the free state (in metal coordinated form) was achieved only very recently in this laboratory⁵⁻⁸ and elsewhere^{9,10}. In this work we summarize some of our findings.

Azo ligands, metals and synthetic strategy

The azopyridines **1** and **2**, generally abbreviated as L, were explored as ligands because of their documented facile reducibility in solution to anion radical species^{4,11-13}. These ligands have excellent affinities for the π-basic metal ions specially ruthenium(II) and osmium(II). In this work we shall limit ourselves to the case of ruthenium(II).

Since the synthesis of crystalline anion radical species could not be achieved via the reduction of preformed complexes of L, we searched for a qualitatively different synthetic route. We looked for a starting material in which the obligatory reducing equivalent as well as certain radical stabilizing features are already built-in. It was hoped that the

reaction of such a material with L might afford Ru(L⁻) directly. Here L⁻ is the anion radical ligand,

In practice, hydrides¹⁴ **3** and **4** turned out to be excellent starting materials, the reducing equivalent being supplied by the hydridic ligand, eq. (2).

Selected radical chelates isolated by this route are collected in Table 1.

Table 1 Representative radical and nonradical complexes

[Ru ^{II} (pap ⁻)(Cl)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂], 5a	[Ru ^{II} (pap)(Cl)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ PF ₆], 5a⁺ PF ₆ ⁻
[Ru ^{II} (Clpap ⁻)(Cl)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂], 5b	[Ru ^{II} (Clpap)(Cl)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ PF ₆], 5b⁺ PF ₆ ⁻
[Ru ^{II} (abp ⁻)(Cl)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂], 5c	[Ru ^{II} (abp)(Cl)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ PF ₆], 5c⁺ PF ₆ ⁻
[Ru ^{II} (abp ⁻) ₂ (CO)(PPh ₃)], 8	[Ru ^{II} (pal)(H)(Cl)(CO)(PPh ₃)], 7
[Ru ^{II} (abp)(abp ⁻)(CO)(PPh ₃)PF ₆], 8⁺ PF ₆ ⁻	[Ru ^{II} (abp)(H)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ PF ₆], 9⁺ PF ₆ ⁻
[Ru ^{II} (abp ⁻)(H)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂], 9	[Ru ^{II} (Clpap)(H)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ PF ₆], 10⁺ PF ₆ ⁻

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Isolation of Ru(L⁻) species

These belong to the structural type 5 where N_a and N_p represent coordinated azo and pyridyl nitrogen atoms, respectively. A representative example is [Ru^{II}(pap⁻)(Cl)(CO)(PPh₃)₂], **5a**. Upon boiling **3** with excess pap in dry heptane under an inert (nitrogen) atmosphere, the crystal-

5

line green complex **5a** deposits from the reaction mixture in nearly quantitative yield. The choice of dry hydrocarbon as the reaction medium is crucial for the synthesis of the radical products. In polar solvents, there is a strong tendency to form nonradical species, *vide supra*.

In order to authenticate the role of the azo function in sustaining radical species, the isoelectronic aldimine function as in the ligand, pal, **6** was used as a control. Here only the red hydridic complex [Ru^{II}(pal)(H)(Cl)(CO)(PPh₃)], **7** (N_{im} = imine nitrogen) could be isolated. The π* orbital of the aldimine function is too unstable to accept an electron unlike the azo function.

pal

6

7

Species of type Ru^{II}(H)(L⁻), Ru^{II}(L⁻)₂ and Ru^{II}(L⁻)(L)

The results with **3** encouraged us to explore the reactions of the dihydride **4** with azo ligands (eqs. 3 and 4). The reaction of **4** with three-fold excess abp in boiling dry benzene under nitrogen afforded the diradical bis-chelate [Ru^{II}(abp⁻)₂(CO)(PPh₃)], **8**. When abp is used in a smaller excess the hydridic mono-chelate monoradical [Ru^{II}(abp⁻)(H)(CO)(PPh₃)₂], **9** accumulated in solution and could be isolated. Treatment of **8** with

8

9

NH₄PF₆ in wet dichloromethane-acetonitrile medium afforded the stable monoradical bis-chelate salt [Ru^{II}(abp⁻)(abp)(CO)(PPh₃)]PF₆, **8⁺**PF₆⁻.

8⁺PF₆⁻

The controlled reaction of **4** with two-fold excess of Clpap in dry boiling benzene yielded [Ru^{II}(Clpap⁻)(H)(CO)(PPh₃)₂], **10** whose isomeric geometry is different from that of the corresponding abp⁻ compound **9**. Attempted synthesis of Clpap analogs of the radical bis-chelates **8** and **8⁺**PF₆⁻ was unsuccessful.

10

Nonradical congeners

Relevant species are listed in Table 1. In general, solutions of the radical species are stable in dry hydrocarbon solvents even in presence of oxygen. However, addition of weak acids like acetic acid and salicylic acid to the solution leads to rapid oxidation to the corresponding nonradical congener presumably due to the reaction of eq. (5),

It has been found that wet acetonitrile solutions of NH_4PF_6 are sufficiently acidic (hydrolysis) to bring about the above oxidation and this has provided the basis for practical synthesis of nonradical congeners. Thus the addition of an acetonitrile solution of NH_4PF_6 to a stirred dichloromethane solution of a type 5 radical under ambient conditions affords red colored diamagnetic 5^+ isolated in excellent yields as the PF_6^- salt. The synthesis of 8^+PF_6^- from

8 described in the previous section is based on the same principle.

Magnetism and EPR spectra

The room temperature magnetic moments of the polycrystalline monoradical complexes correspond to one unpaired electron (Table 2). The samples display a strong EPR signal near $g = 2.00$ with peak-to-peak line widths ΔH_{pp} in the range 10–20 G (Table 2, Fig. 1). The effective magnetic moment of the diradical 8 is $\sim 1.4 \mu_B$ at room temperature

Table 2. Bulk magnetic moments at 298 K and EPR g values in solid state

Compd. no.	μ_{eff}, μ_B 298 K	g values ($\Delta H_{pp}, \text{G}$)	
		298 K	77 K
5a	1.89	2.000(24)	2.001(29)
5b	1.80	2.000(26)	2.000(30)
5c	1.86	2.001(16)	2.001(20)
8^+PF_6^-	1.79	2.003(19)	1.999(13)
9	1.83	2.002(13)	2.003(15)
10	1.80	2.000(9)	2.003(12)

and the susceptibility decreases progressively with temperature suggesting the presence of antiferromagnetic coupling. Further studies are in progress. The nonradical Ru(L) species are uniformly diamagnetic and display normal ^1H NMR spectra in solution.

Reduction potential and CO stretch

In dichloromethane solution, the mono-chelate $\text{RuL}^{\cdot-}$

Fig. 1. Powder EPR spectrum of 5a in the X-band (9.11 GHz) at 298 K. Instrument settings : power, 28 dB; modulation, 100 kHz; sweep center, 3200 G; sweep width, 1000 G; sweep time, 240 s.

species displays a quasireversible response due to the couple of eq. (6) near -0.4 V (Table 3). The bis-chelates show two successive couples separated by ~ 0.4 V, eqs. (7) and (8),

The $E_{1/2}$ of the pap complex 5a is more negative than that of the abp complex 5c consistent with the π -acidity gradation : pap < abp. There is also a qualitative correlation between the $E_{1/2}$ values and CO stretching frequencies (Table 3) which follow the order $\text{Rupap}^{\cdot-} < \text{Ruabp}^{\cdot-}$. The superior π -acidity of abp diminishes the extent of back-bonding to the CO ligand. Further, for a given azo ligand the CO stretching frequency increases upon radical oxidation ($\text{RuL}^{\cdot-} < \text{RuL}$) representing the decline in the extent of net back-bonding to the coordinated CO in going from the anion radical to the nonradical species. Back-bonding to CO and PPh_3 ligands is believed to play a significant role in stabilizing the azo anion radical complexes.

Table 3. Electrochemical^a and IR spectral^b data

Compd. no.	$E_{1/2}, \text{V}(\Delta E_{pc}, \text{mV})/\text{L}/\text{L}^{\cdot-}$	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}, \text{cm}^{-1}$
5a	-0.40(120)	1923
5a ⁺		1960
5c	-0.30(120)	1955
5c ⁺		1980
8	0.10(100), -0.28(100)	1960
8 ⁺	0.10(90), -0.25(90)	2000

^aIn 0.1 M $\text{Et}_4\text{NClO}_4\text{-CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ vs SCE. ^bIn KBr disk.

Structure

Among the radical species, the X-ray structures of 5a,

$8^+PF_6^-$, have been determined. The nonradical complexes, $5b^+PF_6^-$, $5c^+PF_6^-$, $9^+PF_6^-$ and $10^+PF_6^-$ have also been structurally characterized. The N–N distances in the radical and nonradical species have been found to lie in the ranges 1.28–1.29 and 1.33–1.37 Å, respectively, signifying that in the radical species, the unpaired electron has substantial azo character.

Selected distances of $5a$ and $5b^+$ are compared in Table 4. This provides a unique opportunity for comparing the azo and azo anion radical N–N lengths in the same environment and for assessing the effect of radical formation on

Table 4 Selected bond distances (Å) and their estimated standard deviations in parentheses for $5a$ and $5b^+PF_6^- 2CH_2Cl_2$

	$5a$	$5b^+PF_6^- 2CH_2Cl_2$
Ru-P1	2 416(2)	2 429(2)
Ru-P2	2 400(2)	2 420(2)
Ru-N1	2 154(6)	2 125(5)
Ru-N3	2 087(6)	2 042(5)
Ru-Cl	2 440(2)	2 391(2)
Ru-C48	1 856(10)	1 874(8)
O1-C48	1 091(9)	1 126(8)
N2-N3	1 333(7)	1 293(7)

other bond parameters. In uncoordinated azo compounds and hydrazines, the N–N distances are 1.25^{15–17} and 1.45¹⁸ Å, respectively. In $5a$ the distance has an intermediate value, 1.333(7) Å. A plot of N–N bond order versus bond length in the range N–N, $N^{\cdot\cdot}N$ and $N=N$ is presented in Fig. 2. In $5b^+$, the N–N distance is still 0.04 Å longer than 1.25 Å due

Fig. 2. A plot of N–N bond order versus bond length

to strong $t_2-\pi^*$ (azo) back-bonding^{11,12,19–23}. In the plot of Fig. 2, the length in $5b^+$ corresponds to a bond order of 1.7. Back-bonding to π^* (azo) is expected to become unimportant upon anion radical formation and there is indeed a 0.04 Å increase in the Ru–N(azo) distance between $5b^+$ and $5a$. The CO and PPh₃ ligands play a stabilizing role by contributing more to back-bonding in $5a$ than in $5b^+$, as can be

seen in bond length data and in ν_{CO} values (Table 3), (a 35 cm^{-1} decrease between 5^+ and 5).

The remarkable feature of the structure of $8^+PF_6^-$ is the difference in the two N–N lengths : 1.284(6) (ring A) and 1.336(6) Å (ring B), corroborating radical localization in ring B. The Ru–N(pyridine) lengths 2.116(4) and 2.112(4) Å in rings A and B are nearly equal. On the other hand, the corresponding Ru–N(azo), 2.013(4) and 2.083(4) Å are well discriminated due to radical localization in ring B. The decrease of Ru–azo back-bonding in going from $Ru^{II}(abp)$ to $Ru^{II}(abp^{\cdot-})$ lengthens the Ru–N(azo) distance in the latter.

Frontier orbitals

To gain insight into the approximate composition of the frontier orbitals, extended Hückel calculations were performed on simplified models (PPh₃ replaced by PH₃). The case of $[Ru^{II}(pap^{\cdot-})(Cl)(CO)(PPh_3)_2]$, $5a$ is representative. The molecule has no symmetry (Cl) and there is considerable mixing of atomic orbitals. The half-filled HOMO (MO 46, $E = -10.81$ eV) and the LUMO (MO 45, $E = -8.83$ eV) are depicted in Fig. 3. The half-filled HOMO is ~45% azo- π^* in character with significant metal (~20%), pendant phenyl (~15%) and pyridyl (~10%) contributions. The LUMO lying ~2 eV above the HOMO is more or less pure (~90%) pyridyl- π^* in nature with a very small azo contribution. MO 47 ($E = -11.91$ eV) lying below the HOMO is primarily (~65%) metal- t_2 in character. This analysis shows that complexes of type 5 can be roughly described as azo anion radicals species but with significant metal and aromatic (phenyl plus pyridyl) character. This is also reflected in the bond length parameters, such as the elongation of both Ru–N(azo) and Ru–N(pyridine) lengths in going from $5a$ to $5b^+$. Significantly, the former elongates more than the latter. In going from $5a$ to $5a^+$, MO 46 becomes the LUMO and the HOMO is primarily metal- t_2 in character.

The electronic bands of selected radical and nonradical species are listed in Table 5. The radical band in the 500–600 nm region is assigned to the HOMO \rightarrow LUMO transition. It is essentially an intraligand excitation of the anion radical electron from the azo to the pyridyl function. The band near 500 nm in 5^+ is assigned to HOMO(t_2) \rightarrow LUMO

Table 5 Electronic spectral data at 298 K

Compd no	λ_{max} , nm (ϵ^a , $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)
$5a^b$	580(5400), 460(4200) ^c , 370(15000)
$5a^+d$	500(2400) ^c , 450(2600) ^c , 380(9800)
8^b	568(4250), 368(13950)
8^+d	556(2660) ^c , 489(3100), 349(10880)

^aExtinction coefficient ^bIn benzene ^cShoulder ^dIn dichloromethane

Fig. 3. Frontier molecular orbitals of 5a Only metal and azo ligand atoms are shown for clarity

charge transfer. An EHMO study on **8** and 8^+ is in progress. The main purpose is to probe the origin of radical localization.

Conclusion :

It is demonstrated that hydrides **3** and **4** are excellent starting materials for synthesizing crystalline Ru^{II} azo anion radical species of types $Ru^{II}(L^{\bullet-})$, $Ru^{II}(L^{\bullet-})_2$ and $Ru^{II}(L^{\bullet-})(L)$. The use of dry hydrocarbon solvent is crucial for the synthesis. In polar media facile conversion to nonradical species occurs in presence of weak acids including water.

Structure determination, reduction potential and spectral data suggest that back-bonding to CO and PPh_3 ligands play a significant role in stabilizing the azo anion radical complexes. The trend of N–N bond length in the triad hydrazine, azo anion radical and uncoordinated azo have been correlated.

The spin bearing HOMO of the radical species is ~50% azo- π^* in character, the LUMO lying ~2 eV above the HOMO is more or less pure pyridyl- π^* in character. The HOMO \rightarrow LUMO transition occurs in the visible region near 550 nm. The origin of the observed spin localization in $Ru^{II}(L^{\bullet-})(L)$ is under scrutiny.

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